

Hybrid Provision of Energy based on Reliability and Resiliency by Integration of Dc Equipment

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Hybrid Grid Enabling Solutions

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List of Abbreviations

FEM	Finite Element Method
CFD	Computational Fluid Dynamics
CAD	Computer Aided Design
IAC	Internal Arc Classification

Executive Summary

This report summarises the reasons of the necessity of performing arc fault tests and arc fault calculations for new hybrid AC&DC-grid concepts which are targeted in HYPERRIDE. It gives an overview about the normative references and describes the workflow of doing arc fault calculations and how to validate them with arc fault experiments. It describes the starting point for the physical model building which is necessary for both, the room average method and the Finite Element Method (FEM). The FEM-method use Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) and solves the Navier Stokes equations. First experimental results and a FEM calculation are discussed. A new enclosure is presented, which will be used in task T3.4 for performing systematic AC&DC arc fault experiments. The complicated physics of arcing requires a strong interaction of theory and experiments. Therefore a work flow for doing arc fault simulations in combination with arc fault experiments has been worked out.

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope of the Document

This document summarises the reasons for the necessity of performing arc fault tests and arc fault calculations for new hybrid AC&DC-grids concepts which are targeted in HYPERRIDE. It describes the workflow of performing arc fault calculations and how to validate them with arc fault experiments. It describes the physical model building as a prerequisite for calculations, which utilise the room average method or the FEM. The FEM-calculations will be done on the basis of experimental results with the commercial program COMSOL.

1.2 Structure of the Document

The motivation for doing arc fault experiments and calculations is given in Section 1.3. Section 2 discusses the definition of the thermal transfer coefficient, gives an overview about the equations needed to describe the pressure development and the hot gas exhaust and shows the nonlinear physical properties of hot air. Section 3 shows a first arc fault experiment and the results of a first arc fault FEM calculation. Section 4 proposes the workflow for arc fault calculations in strong interaction with experiments for validation. The whole deliverable is finally concluded in Section 5.

1.3 Motivation

Internal arc faults in high power AC&DC-grids can develop locally temperatures far above 10000 K, pressure blast waves up to one bar and huge hot gas releases. They are hazardous for human, electrical energy systems and buildings. There are active arc fault detection and extinction systems on the market (Fulchiron, Brandt, Douchin, & al., 2017). But these systems are quite expensive, maintenance intensive and their proper functionality over decades is not guaranteed. Further disadvantages of these systems are undesired operations like false positive- or false negative events. This gives these systems an ad-on-status and restrict their broad dissemination. More powerful grids, a higher sensitivity for potential risks as well as more rigorous normative references and governmental obligations requires at least an arc fault evaluation to show a passive arc fault security of the new concepts for hybrid AC&DC-grids. The physics of DC-arcs is different in comparison to the physics of AC-arcs, because of the lack of zero-crossings in the current. This makes DC-arcs more dangerous, because once ignited there is a much lower tendency of self-extinction. Also, the sources of DC-current are different: converters (diodes and thyristors), batteries, capacitors, hydrogen-oxygen fuel cells and photo-voltaics instead of generators and transformers.

Arc fault tests of distribution- and switchgear-enclosures are time intensive and expensive. In the LV-AC-world these tests are well established and experimentally performed due to normative regulations like IEC/TR 61641 ed. 3.0:2014 (Enclosed low-voltage switchgear and control gear assemblies - Guide for testing under conditions of arcing due to internal fault).

In the MV-AC-world switchgears, transformer substations and switchgear stations have to be tested according to EN 62271-200, 62271-202 and IEC/TR 61936 (strength of construction, security of persons Internal Arc Classification (IAC)-A and IAC-B). Additionally, the EN 61936 section 7.5 claims that buildings have to withstand pressurisation by arc faults. In cases where

experimental arc fault tests cannot be performed, the proof can be done by computational methods, like the room average or the FEM method.

Normative references for DC tests are now being worked out by IEC TC17: HIGH-VOLTAGE SWITCHGEAR AND CONTROLGEAR, e.g.:

- IEC TS 62271-5 ED1; High-voltage switchgear and controlgear - Part 5: Common specifications for direct current switchgear
- IEC TS 62271-313 ED1; High-voltage switchgear and controlgear - Part 313: Direct current circuit-breaker
- IEC TS 62271-314 ED1; High-voltage switchgear and controlgear - Part 314: Direct current disconnectors and earthing switches
- IEC TS 62271-315 ED1; High-voltage switchgear and controlgear - Part 315: Direct current (DC) transfer switches
- IEC 62271-317 High-voltage switchgear and control gear - Part 317 DC gas-insulated switchgear assemblies

It has to be distinguished, where the high power DC comes from. When evaluating arc fault safety, the maximal arc fault current and the maximal arc fault power of the feeding grid has to be known. AC-DC/DC-DC converters are being considered as safe sources for the subgrids, because of their integrated current limiting functionality and fast switch-off capability of the semiconductor switches. Also subgrids protected by hybrid DC vacuum circuit breakers are considered to be safe, because of the fast switch off times below 1.5 ms of the hybrid DC vacuum circuit breakers. But what happens, when these devices fail and become the source of arcing, e.g. because of aged, overloaded and exploding semiconductors? Then, the arc fault currents are only limited by the feeding grid and can reach very high values.

Also battery storages and capacitor banks constitute a new source of danger, because of their low intrinsic inductances. They can increase their current to the short circuit value very fast and hold these values for several minutes. E.g. a human fail operation before the circuit breaker or fuse can lead to an unquenchable arcing.

2 Physical Modelling

2.1 Thermal Transfer Coefficient

An overview of physical modelling can be found in (Uzelac, Glinkowski, Del Rio, & al., 2014). In lack of the knowledge of detailed description of the physics of high power arcs, the commonly used starting-point for a computational arc fault evaluation is the definition of a thermal transfer coefficient k_p , e.g.

$$k_p = \frac{Q}{W_{el}} \quad (1)$$

where Q is the the thermal energy corresponding to pressure rise and W_{el} is the electrical energy turnover. A common value for k_p for copper electrodes is 0.4. To get values for k_p , experiments are typically performed in closed compartments and the pressure rise and electric energy turnover is measured. In this work a modification of this definition will be done, because industrial enclosure typically have pressure release paths (see Section 3), like:

- gas release to the cable-cellar
- gas release through flaps on the top to the installation room
- gas ducts to the outside

A density-of-air(ρ)-dependent k_p -factor considers the reduced heat transfer in gases with reduced mass-density and improve the numerical computation stability:

$$k_p(t) = k_{p0} \left(\frac{\rho(t)}{\rho_0} \right)^{0.5} \quad (2)$$

2.2 Basics of Pressure and Hot Gas Release Calculations

A pioneer work at AIT, the computation of arc-fault-induced pressure-loads, was done already in 1993 by (Faltin, Hauer, & Eberhard, 1993). A Fortran program specialised on arc fault pressure calculations in arbitrary shaped rooms was written, which solved the Euler-equations utilising a Finite Difference Method. This program, however, had several disadvantages: (i) a user-friendly interface was missing, (ii) it was not compatible with common Computer Aided Design (CAD)- and FEM- software and (iii) the pressure values showed high amplitude oscillations, also far away from the arc fault. This was probably due to neglecting effective damping mechanisms of air, like viscosity and turbulence and also due to numerical problems of the Finite Difference Method (Faltin, Schlüter, & Schwing, 1998).

In the following a more advanced model based on the Navier-Stokes equations will be discussed. The material time derivative is given by:

$$\frac{d}{dt} = \frac{\partial}{\partial t} + \vec{u} \cdot \vec{\nabla} \quad (3)$$

where \vec{u} is the gas streaming velocity.

With this definition the momentum conservation can be written in a compact form:

$$\rho \frac{d\vec{u}}{dt} = \vec{\nabla} \cdot (-p\vec{I} + \vec{K}) + (\rho - \rho_{ref})\vec{g} \quad (4)$$

where p is the relative pressure, \tilde{I} is the unity tensor and ρ_{ref} is the density of the surrounding air. Note that ρ_{ref} can vary significantly, e.g. when considering a wind park located on mountains.

The viscosity tensor \tilde{K} of a gas (which is a Newtonian fluid) is

$$\tilde{K} = \mu(\vec{\nabla}\vec{u} + (\vec{\nabla}\vec{u})^T) - \frac{2}{3}\mu(\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{u})\tilde{I} \quad (5)$$

where μ stands for the temperature dependent viscosity of air.

The mass conservation is

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot (\rho\vec{u}) = 0. \quad (6)$$

The power conservation is

$$\rho c_p \frac{dT}{dt} + \vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{q} = Q + Q_p \quad (7)$$

where c_p is specific heat capacity at constant pressure, T is the temperature, Q is the electric energy turnover multiplied by the k_p -factor and \vec{q} is the heat flow density. Ficks law is

$$\vec{q} = -k\vec{\nabla}T. \quad (8)$$

The volume changing power is

$$Q_p = \alpha_p T \frac{dp}{dt}. \quad (9)$$

where the thermal expansion coefficient α_p is defined by

$$\alpha_p = -\frac{1}{\rho} \left(\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial T} \right)_p. \quad (10)$$

and is for an ideal gas equal to $-R$.

The ideal gas law $p = \rho RT$ can be used for air up to 6000 K. The aim is to describe the effects of arcing at some distance from the arc and not the description of the complicated behaviour of the arc column itself. This is simply done by enclosing the arc column with an imaginary box, a little bit larger than the arc, leading to $T < 6000$ K within the box. The solution of Equation (7) to Equation (10) are the time- and position-dependent fields $\vec{u}(\vec{r}, t)$, $T(\vec{r}, t)$, $p(\vec{r}, t)$ and $\rho(\vec{r}, t)$. Also pressure waves are possible solutions of these differential equations. In contrast, the Room Average Method cannot describe pressure waves due to its averaging approach.

All differential equation systems require boundary- and initial conditions for solving. Here, some additional simplifications are made:

- $-\vec{n} \cdot \vec{q} = 0$ adiabatic walls,
- $\vec{n} \cdot \vec{u}(\vec{r} \in wall, t) = 0$ no flow through walls, slippery walls,
- $\vec{u}(\vec{r}, t = 0) = 0$ no flow at the begin of experiment,
- $p(\vec{r}, t = 0) = 0$ at the begin of experiment and
- heat input Q in arcing channel or larger reference volume.

The following physics is neglected:

- Radiation: the energy dissipation of arcs due to radiation of is very strong and generally has to be considered. In this work only the effects of pressure waves and hot gases will be described. The radiation cannot leave the steel enclosure and is already included in the k_p -factor.
- No moving arcs: The movement of arcs, e.g. from one cabinet to another, can occur, have to be avoided by a gas tightness and is unpredictable. The description of these phenomenons is due to the coupling with Maxwell's equations highly complex and not in the scope of HYPERRIDE.
- Only laminar flow considered: This serves as a worst-case description for the pressure calculation, because turbulence adds further damping to the system (Faltin et al., 1998).
- Evaporation of Cu-electrodes influence the energy balance and the composition of plasma. These effects are already included in the k_p -factor.
- Further Effects, see e.g. (Uzelac et al., 2014)

2.3 Physical Properties of Hot Air

The physical properties of hot air are massively non-linear due to dissociation and ionisation processes. A pressure dependence of these quantities is not considered because of the narrow relevant pressure range from 0 to 0.6 bar and a weak dependence of these quantities on pressure, which is well understood in the theory of gases. Figure 1 and Figure 2 shows the specific heat capacity and the thermal conductivity of hot air up to 30000 K with its characteristic peaks due to dissociation and ionisation. Figure 3 shows the electric conductivity of air, which is understood with the Saha-equation. These temperature dependencies were implemented in COMSOL.

Figure 1: Specific heat capacity at constant pressure of air up to 30000 K.

Figure 2: Thermal conductivity of air up to 30000 K.

Figure 3: Electrical conductivity of air up to 30000 K.

3 First Experimental Arc Fault Results of Enclosure E1

Figure 4 shows the currents, voltages, power and pressure measured during an arc fault test in the enclosure E1. The pressure sensor was located in the middle of the front door. E1 has the same outer dimensions as the later discusses enclosure E2 (E2 was newly build to match the requirements of fundamental science testings). The measurement has a quite short time of arcing of approximately 10 ms, in comparison with an arc fault test according to IEC/TR 61641, where 250 ms (LV) are required. This, however, gives a good insight on the pressure wave propagation. Only one main arc between busbar 1 and busbar 2 contributes to the main pressure peak (see Figure 4d) and can be interpreted as a DC-arc. Of course Figure 4a indicates, that also arcs between other busbars are burning, but with much lower power.

Figure 4: Results of a short 3-phase AC arc fault experiment as function of time [s]: (a) currents, (b) voltages measured to ground potential, (c) power, (d) pressure.

Enclosure E1 has a pressure release flap on the top, which releases hot gases (see Figure 5). That means that the premise of a closed room is not valid. Therefore the definition of k_p is modified to

$$k_p(t_c) = \frac{V \int_0^{t_c} p(t) dt}{(\kappa - 1) t_c \int_0^{t_c} u(t) i(t) dt} \quad (11)$$

where V is the volume of the enclosure, κ is adiabatic coefficient of air (approximately 1.4) and t_c is a characteristic time which is given by

$$t_c = \frac{L_c}{c}. \quad (12)$$

where L_c is the characteristic length of the enclosure (in this study depending on the place of arc ignition 1 or 2 m) and c is the velocity of sound (ca. 340 m/s).

Figure 5: Exhaust of hot gases during arc fault test of enclosure E1.

3.1 Pressure Calculation

This subsection shows the results obtained by the finite element method calculation. Figure 6 shows the finite element mesh of the enclosure. The automatic, physic determined option, was chosen in COMSOL for the time steps of the calculation.

Figure 6: Finite element mesh.

Figure 7 shows a colour slice plot of relative pressure a short time (0.01 s) after ignition.

Figure 7: Pressure at time 0.01 s after ignition.

Figure 8 shows the velocity of air in a colour slice plot at the time 0.012 s after ignition. The movement of the air with high speed from the place of ignition (in the middle of the enclosure) is clearly visible.

Figure 8: Velocity at the time 0.012 s.

Figure 9 shows the temperature in a slice plot at the time 0.0346 s. The movement of the hot gases to the opened exhaust flap at the top is clearly visible.

Figure 9: Temperature at the time 0.0346 s.

Figure 10 shows three representative pressure evaluation points (top, middle, bottom) and the place of arcing (arc). Figure 11, Figure 12 and Figure 13 show the calculated pressure-time dependencies at representative points located at the door nearby the ground, middle and top of the enclosure. In comparison with Figure 4d a good agreement of the amplitude of the first pressure peak was found, but the damping of pressure is in the model too slow.

Figure 10: colour slice plot of pressure at time 0.01 s after ignition.

Figure 11: Pressure as a function of time in the point 'top'.

Figure 12: Pressure as a function of time in the point 'middle'.

Figure 13: Pressure as a function of time in the point 'bottom'.

4 Enclosure E2 for AC&DC arc fault tests

The new enclosure for AC&DC arc fault tests is shown in Figure 14 (Eaton xEnergy, width = 60 cm, depth = 60 cm, height = 200 cm: $V = 0.72 \text{ m}^3$). It is equipped with 4 bus-bars (Figure 15) and a gas-release flap (Figure 16).

Figure 14: Enclosure E2 for arc fault tests.

Figure 15: Enclosure E2 for arc fault tests: busbars with adjustable arcing gaps.

Figure 16: Enclosure E2 for arc fault tests: pressure release flap. The flap is hold on one side by 2 Nylon-screws M3 × 12.

Arc faults with increasing power will be ignited in enclosure E2 until the destruction of the enclosure. In the AC-world quite long arcing duration times are defined in the IEC-regulations

for experimental arc fault tests, due to the quite long reaction times of fuses or circuit breakers:

- Medium Voltage 1 s
- Low Voltage 250 ms

The maximal thermal load limits the maximal allowed duration of currents in the diodes to 100 ms. Therefore an arcing duration of 100 ms will be chosen, which also enable a good comparison with AC-arcing (5 periods).

The circuit inductance will be in the range of 24 μH and the open circuit voltage will be reduced to 800 V. This reduction is allowed in arc fault testing, because for the arc power turnover only the distance between the busbars and the current is essential (voltage reduction in analogy to EN 62271-200 is possible so long as re-ignition after current zero crossing is given).

In the following an experimental work plan is roughly outlined. The amount of arc fault shots can be estimated by following variations and factors, e.g.:

- current: 5 kA, 15 kA, 25 kA
- DC, 2-phase AC, 3-phase AC
- electrode distance: 2 cm, 5 cm
- repetition because of too early self-extinction or other problems

This gives approximately 18 shots. The more exact number of shots will be chosen during testing according to the quality of measured data, because arc fault tests have very harsh conditions and the proper functionality and lifetime of sensors, enclosures and even testing facilities is not guaranteed at all. Figure 17 shows the proposed workflow for arc fault tests, calculation and validation of calculation procedures.

Figure 17: Workflow for doing arc fault tests, calculations and validations of the calculations.

5 Conclusions

DC-arcing is different to AC-arcing due to different physics and different current sources. In the MV and LV AC-world normative references are well established, which claim an experimental proof of components regarding the strength of construction and the safety of persons. In the DC-world normative references are now being worked out and the votings are planned in 2022. Technical details about DC-arc fault safety are still missing in the new normative DC references.

First arc fault experiments were done and compared with finite element method simulations. A good agreement of the amplitude of the first pressure peak was found, the damping of pressure is in the model improvable.

A work flow for doing arc fault simulations in combination with arc fault experiments (in Task T3.4) was worked out. The strong interaction of theory and experiments during the task is necessary due to the complicated physics.

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